

The Neuropathology of Alzheimer's in Down Syndrome Cortical Organoids

Aghili, Leila, Shainsky, Dina, Morris, Kevin, Yamamoto, Vicky, Kateb, Babak

ABSTRACT

Down syndrome (DS) is a genetic disorder with an abnormality in chromosome 21. By the age of 40, most patients with DS exhibit hallmarks of Alzheimer's disease (AD), manifesting as the accumulation of plaques and tangles in their brains. Our understanding of Alzheimer's and DS neuropathology at the molecular level before the onset of clinical pathology is largely unexplored.

The study by Zhao et al. explored induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC) and iPSC-derived 3D cortical organoids to model Alzheimer's disease in DS. iPSC-derived DS cortical organoids have a much higher immunoreactivity of amyloid beta (A β) antibodies and a significantly higher number of amyloid plaques than control organoids.

INTRODUCTION

Down syndrome (DS), also known as trisomy 21, is a genetic condition characterized by three full or partial copies of human chromosome 21 (HSA21), the smallest human chromosome in all or most cells. In the United States, approximately 6000 babies are born with DS each year.

People with DS show a reduced total brain volume as well as brain neuropathology at a young age. Some of the pathological changes observed in the brains of people with DS include altered dendritic spine morphology, hypocellularity, aging-dependent neuronal loss, and abnormal synaptic density, which have been shown to affect several brain areas, including the cerebellum.

Early onset Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a major concern for DS patients, all of whom exhibit the characteristic neuropathology of AD by the age of 40 years, and 70% of whom develop AD dementia after the age of 50. The life expectancy for people with DS has more than doubled over the past 30 years. As such, their increased risk for developing AD dementia has become a significant concern.

The brains of people over the age of 40 with DS and the brains of patients with AD dementia have similar patterns and levels of amyloid- β (A β) deposition and in terms of the distribution of neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs). The regions where NFTs accumulate significantly include the hippocampus, entorhinal cortex, and neocortex. Additional similarities, such as increased levels of plaque-associated proteins, together with microglial activation, astrogliosis, inflammation, and oxidative stress, are observed in DS and AD brains.

There is a common pathogenic mechanism thought to exist between DS and AD. Various genes, including the APP (amyloid precursor protein), BACE2 (beta-secretase 2), PICALM (Phosphatidylinositol binding clathrin assembly protein), and APOE (Apolipoprotein E) genes, have been reported to cause or contribute to early onset AD. Trisomy for the APP gene alone is sufficient to lead to the development of AD pathology and AD dementia in people with DS.

METHODS

Cortical organoids were generated from iPSCs as previously described (Camp et al., 2015; Trujillo et al., 2019; Yao et al., 2020). Then organoids were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde for 30 minutes and then transferred to 30% sucrose solution at 4°C overnight. Then Cryopreserved organoids were embedded in OCT and sectioned into 14 μ m-thick slices for immunofluorescence staining. The sections were then incubated with the primary antibody diluted in PBS with 5% BSA overnight, and Alexa 488 and Alexa 555 conjugated secondary antibodies to specific IgG types for one h.

Amyloid plaque staining on organoid sections was performed using the Amylo-Glo RTD amyloid plaque stain reagent. Detergent soluble and insoluble fractions of amyloid beta (A β 40, A β 42) and total Tau were also quantified using Elisa kits.

The research methodology implemented is an evidence-based rapid review. Literature and database searches were conducted, and extracted information was assessed.

Fig.1: How does the Down Syndrome brain parallel and differ from Alzheimer's brain. used with permission

RESULTS

A major AD-like pathology in DS patients is an accumulation of A β . There is a much higher immunoreactivity of amyloid beta (A β) and amyloid plaques in DS iPSC-derived cortical organoids plaques than in control organoids.

The presence of A β accumulation in DS organoids was examined in three different methods as below:

First, two different antibodies, including D54D2 and 82E1, were examined on 8-week and 12-week organoids that recognize A β 37-42 and A β 40-42, respectively. The D54D2 antibody was more immunoreactive in both age group organoids than control organoids.

Second, for staining the amyloid plaques in the organoid sections, Amylo-Glo reagent was used to stain the amyloid plaque in the organoid sections. As a result, there is much more stain in DS organoids for Amylo-Glo than control organoids.

Third, for quantifying the amyloid beta, including the A β 40 and A β 42, ELISA was used in the detergent soluble and insoluble fractions of DS and control organoids. Twelve weeks DS organoids showed a significantly increased of A β 42/A β 40 than that in control organoids at the same age.

DISCUSSION

Although all DS patients studied over the age of 40 exhibits AD-like neuropathology and abnormal A β accumulation and neurofibrillary tangles, the progression of the disease and the onset of that before the clinical beginning is still obscure and much less explored. For simulating key endogenous neurodevelopment events and having a model system to study the AD-like disease pathology in DS, iPSC-derived 3D organoids are used.

In summary, AD-like pathophysiological phenotype, including abnormal A β accumulation, was mimicked in DS iPSC-derived brain organoids. In other words, molecular pathobiology in DS starts early in brain development and can be used as a model system to study AD-like pathology and its progress before the clinical onset of the disease.

REFERENCES

- Zhao, H. H., & Haddad, G. G. (2022). Alzheimer's disease like neuropathology in Down syndrome cortical organoids. *Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience*, 16.
- Asim, A., Kumar, A., Muthuswamy, S., Jain, S., & Agarwal, S. (2015). Down syndrome: an insight of the disease. *Journal of biomedical science*, 22(1), 1-9.
- Mégarbané, A., Ravel, A., Mircher, C., Sturtz, F., Grattau, Y., Rethoré, M. O., ... & Mobley, W. C. (2009). The 50th anniversary of the discovery of trisomy 21: the past, present, and future of research and treatment of Down syndrome. *Genetics in Medicine*, 11(9), 611-616.
- Camp, J. G., Badsha, F., Florio, M., Kanton, S., Gerber, T., Wilsch-Bräuningner, M., ... & Treutlein, B. (2015). Human cerebral organoids recapitulate gene expression programs of fetal neocortex development. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(51), 15672-15677.
- Trujillo, C. A., & Muotri, A. R. (2018). Brain organoids and the study of neurodevelopment. *Trends in molecular medicine*, 24(12), 982-990.
- Yao, H., Wu, W., Cerf, I., Zhao, H. W., Wang, J., Negraes, P. D., ... & Haddad, G. G. (2020). Methadone interrupts neural growth and function in human cortical organoids. *Stem Cell Research*, 49, 102065.
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